

DIGITALIZATION OF CRIMINAL PROCEDURAL MEASURES OF COERCION

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Abstract. The article provides a comparative-legal analysis of digitalization criminal procedural measures of coercion. Criminal proceedings in order to simplify and ensure speed, the proposals and recommendations on the digitalization of the pre-trial and court stage are scientifically substantiated.

Key words: measures of coercion, preventive measures, digitalization.

Procedural measures of coercion can be applied at any stage of the criminal process and researching their terms is considered an urgent task. In particular, there are many cases of long-term detention of pre-accused in prison and in order¹ to eliminate such cases, according to the amendment introduced to the Criminal Procedural Code on August 29, 2001, the maximum period of detention in prison is six months, on August 29, 2017 reduced by another five months under the March amendment. In the situation where the reforms regarding the improvement of procedural terms, the use of the institution of "Habeas Corpus Act" in the criminal process are constantly developing, a wider and deeper analysis of the current procedural law norms, the reduction of the terms of keeping a person in prison or house arrest and other measures of coercion much as possible and through this it is necessary to further liberalize the criminal-legal sphere. Because currently, the requests for detention from a single inquiry to the courts are 19,642 in 2021; 10,078 in 2020 there were 138 petitions to extend the term of imprisonment in 2020 it was 344² and these indicators require excessive procedural time and costs not only in court, but also at the investigation stage.

First of all, the order of detention of the accused with the consent of the court has a long history. The law named "Habeas Corpus Act" adopted in England on May 26, 1679³ is recognized as the first document in the history of mankind that limited arbitrary detention. It states that "No free citizen can be detained, imprisoned, deprived of his property, declared an outlaw, or exiled without a

¹In particular, the term of imprisonment was first set at 9 months in the Criminal Procedural Law of 1959 and was changed to 18 months by the law of November 28, 1989.

² Statistical data of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

³ Criminal proceedings. Instructional manual. -T.: TSUL. 2008. -P. 287-288.

court order." In the "Habeas Corpus Act" the application of the measures of coercion is guaranteed to be considered in an open court session with the participation of the detainee and his defense attorney and was reflected in the CPL of Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Russia, Moldavia, Ukraine and Estonia⁴.

Preventive measures in the form of imprisonment or house arrest, which are the most serious of the measures of coercion are aimed at ensuring the execution of the sentence and preventing the attempts that hinder the determination of the truth is considered a measure to prevent investigation and court evasion or criminal activity.

In particular, from January 1, 2008, among the measures of coercion at the stage of proceedings before the court, judicial control over the use of preventive measure of detention was established, as the next important social event in terms of respect for human rights and freedoms. It was ensured that no one could be imprisoned without a warrant. As a result, new institutions of the criminal procedure appeared, such as "considering the issue of permission to detain a person at a court session", "extending the term of detention by the court", "reviewing the court decision issued in this regard at the appeals instance". It is important to study the procedural terms that regulate these institutions to conduct extensive research.

It should be noted that Law No. 373 of September 4, 2014 on the CPL of the Republic of Uzbekistan according to the amendment and addition, the institution of house arrest was also introduced. Criminal courts have been given the power to authorize detention or house arrest as a preventive measure and to consider extending the period of detention or house arrest, as well as extending the period of detention. When deciding the first issue, the court does not decide whether the person is guilty or innocent, but only discusses the issue of conducting the investigation with or without separating him from society. These measures of coercion are applied to accused persons and in exceptional cases - to persons suspected of having committed a crime. Next, the suspect must be charged within ten days of his arrest. Otherwise, the preventive measure will be canceled and the person will be released from prison or house arrest .

According to Article 226 of the CPL, the period of detention is a maximum of forty-eight hours from the moment of the person's actual detention (the moment of actual restriction of the rights to free movement). Detention may be extended for an additional forty-eight hours by the court's decision when necessary and

⁴ Mirzaev A.A., Tukhtasheva U.A. Implementation of the Habeas Corpus Institute and the National Law in Uzbekistan: cost and perspective. -T. 2019. -P.58.

sufficient grounds are presented by the investigator, investigator or prosecutor:

- for the parties to submit additional evidence on the justification or unfoundedness of the application of a preventive measure in the form of detention or house arrest;
- if detention or house arrest is refused and bail is chosen, the period of detention of the suspect or the accused is extended by the court to a maximum of forty-eight hours to allow for bail, if the bail is not posted within the specified period, the request for the application of a preventive measure in the form of imprisonment or house arrest is considered to be satisfied.

In extending the retention period, we do not think it is necessary to extend it to 48 hours, for example, it can be extended to 8 or 24 hours. In this regard, U.Tukhtasheva's views are close to ours, and the holding period can be extended several times, but the extension period should not exceed 48 hours in total ⁵.

However, regarding the adequacy of the detention period (48 + 48 hours) and the issue of indictment, it should be noted that there are conflicting opinions in this regard. For example, V.Shadrin believes that the announcement of guilt to the suspect after a period of ten days is contrary to the requirement of ⁶ speedy announcement of guilty actions to the person defined in international norms .

Measures should be taken ⁷ to prove the criminal's guilt before he is caught, not after he is caught .

N.Koshaev, in practice, based on traditions, from the moment when sufficient evidence for accusation is gathered, to announce guilt at any stage of the investigation, in some cases to unreasonably delay the implementation of these actions, to arrest the suspect as a preventive measure. He expressed his opinion that in these cases, sufficient evidence was not collected during the ten-day period, and there were no cases of declaring him guilty ⁸.

It is not appropriate to detain a suspect who has been detained for forty-eight hours and sometimes for an extended period of forty-eight hours and charge him for ten days. The announcement of guilt to the suspect after such periods is defined in the second part of Article 9 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, which was adopted in 1966 and which the Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to in 1995: It is contrary to the requirement that every person who is detained shall be informed of the reasons for his detention at the time of his detention and immediately informed of the charge against him.

⁵ Tukhtasheva U.A. That work. -T., 2007. -P. 42.

⁶ Shadrin V.S. Obespechenie prav lichnosti pri rassledovanii prespleniy. -M.: "Yurlitinform", 2000. -P. 36.

⁷ Sharafutdinov A. Strategic directions of preliminary investigation // Huquq pravo Law, 2005. April-June. -P. 45.

⁸ Koshaev N. Involvement of the accused and announcement of guilt. Right and duty, 2009. -4. -P. 61.

Therefore, it is better to declare the guilt during the measure of detention for a reasonable period of time rather than applying the preventive measure of detention against the suspect .

Restriction of constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens starts from the first moments when a person is involved as a participant in criminal proceedings. Therefore, ensuring its protection should also start from this period⁹. Such restrictions legally limit the discretion of the investigator when choosing the time to charge the suspect. Regarding this, the documents of the "International Association of Prosecutors" established in June 1995 with the approval of the UN state that arresting a person is only the authority of the judge, and the detained person 1-2 will be notified that he will be brought to court within a day.

Such an approach was chosen much earlier in the legislation of many foreign countries, including Russia and Kyrgyzstan, where a person must be detained for up to 48 hours and charged during this period . In Moldova and Norway, this period is 24 hours; 48 hours in France, Germany and Italy; In England it is 36 hours¹⁰.

In this matter, the following numbers can be cited from our practice. For example, in 2021, 19 447 custody motions were granted by the courts, but 195 were later denied¹¹ custody.

Based on the above considerations, it can be said that to ensure the protection of a person's constitutional right to freedom from the first moments when he is involved as a participant in the criminal process and to quickly solve it on the basis of digital technologies, it is appropriate to make the following changes to the new version of the CPL: the first part of the article 243: "Preventive measures in the form of detention or house arrest are only applied to the accused can be used". Part 6 of Article 243 of the Criminal Procedural Law: "The motion for detention or the application of a preventive measure in the form of house arrest shall be submitted at the court session within four hours from the moment the materials are received by electronic means , but will be considered in the video conference mode no later than the maximum period of stay".

⁹ Inogomjonova Z.F. Judicial control in criminal proceedings and problems of its implementation. diss. of DSc. -T., 2006. -P. 21.

¹⁰ Ugolovno-protsessualnoe pravo Rossiyskoy Federatsii: Uchebnik / pod red. P.A. Lupinskoy, L.A. Voskobitova. - M.: Norma, Infra-M , 2018 . -S. 45-50 .

¹¹ Statistical data of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

